

GRIFFITH COLLEGE DUBLIN

Management & Organisational Behaviour Assignment 2024

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Case Study Scenario and Copyright Statement

This assignment is based on a proprietary and copyrighted case study examining the challenges faced by a pharmaceutical sales company operating in Ireland, specifically focusing on the design and optimization of their sales force bonus structure to better align incentives with client goals, ensure fairness among representatives, and maintain budget constraints; the original case study is not publicly available, and this document presents my own detailed interpretation, critical analysis, and conclusions derived solely from that material.

Summary of the Case Study Scenario (Rewritten)

The case study describes a company that provides outsourced sales teams for pharmaceutical products across Ireland. The company's recent challenge involved adapting its bonus system to motivate sales representatives effectively, especially as they transitioned from prescription medications to over-the-counter (OTC) products sold primarily in pharmacies and retail stores.

The original bonus structure, based mainly on individual sales figures, was perceived as unfair and demotivating by many team members. Multiple iterations of the incentive scheme were introduced, incorporating factors like pharmacy visits, product visibility on shelves, and client-specific goals such as maintaining perfect product displays and stock levels.

Key issues included regional sales disparities, difficulty in tracking true product recommendations by pharmacists, and the risk of inaccurate self-reporting by representatives. The company's leadership aimed to develop a system that balanced motivating sales reps, meeting client expectations for in-store activity, and controlling costs within a fixed bonus budget.

This case highlights the complexities of managing performance incentives in a fragmented and competitive market environment, emphasizing the importance of aligning business goals with fair and transparent reward systems.

Executive Summary

The analysis of *Drug Sales Ltd.* in parts A1-7 and B of the report reveals several key challenges that the company is facing at its current stage of development. Specifically, issues have been identified concerning an ineffective motivation system, a rigid organisational structure, and a lack of a culture that fosters innovation. A bonus system primarily based on sales results has proven to be demotivating, and the lack of cooperation between employees limits the organisation's effectiveness. Additionally, the rigid organisational hierarchy and limited employee autonomy hinder the company's ability to respond quickly to changing market conditions.

The proposed changes in response to these issues include implementing a more equitable bonus system, increasing employee autonomy, and fostering a culture of cooperation and innovation. Furthermore, altering the organisational structure to be more flexible and promoting open communication and trust could significantly improve employee motivation and commitment and enhance the company's operational effectiveness. These proposals can potentially contribute to the long-term success and increased competitiveness of *Drug Sales Ltd.*, enabling it to adapt more swiftly to new market.

The author utilised several theories, explained and applied throughout the report, to draw conclusions and formulate recommendations for *Drug Sales Ltd.* regarding improving their motivation system. While writing this report, the author's perspective on the problem evolved. Initially, and even now, the author remains sceptical about the feasibility of fully analysing such issues without a complete understanding of the individuals involved. Humans are inherently complex, making it impossible to draw comprehensive conclusions solely from a case study. A case study cannot provide the depth of information that real-life interaction with individuals can offer.

However, through the process of writing this report, the author realised and acknowledged that, even in real life, a supervisor has limited time to get to know their team members in-depth. They must often work with incomplete data and strive to implement universal changes that will foster the company's growth. This understanding highlights the importance of

balancing theoretical approaches with practical, scalable solutions in addressing organisational challenges.

A1: Motivation and Job Satisfaction

After reviewing the bonus structure system at *Drug Sales Ltd.*, it appears that Ethan Carter and his management team, like many other business owners, are not fully aware of how important it is to motivate their employees properly.

“In 1959, Herzberg, Mausner and Snyderman published the two-factor model of work motivation” (Mohammed Alshmemri *et al.*, 2017, p.12). According to *Herzberg's theory*, factors such as recognition, achievement, responsibility, and professional development lead to higher levels of motivation and job satisfaction. In our case, the only factor we can consider as a motivational one is the financial bonus that the best sales representatives receive. However, over time, this ceases to be seen as a motivational reward and becomes a standard (*Herzberg's Theory*, 2014).

From my observations, although unsupported by direct evidence, we relatively quickly become accustomed to current social conditions and see them as a mandatory standard. One could say that people become “addicted” to these conditions, and just like in the case of addiction, when one of these factors is taken away, they begin to feel significant discomfort. Offering a monetary reward slowly becomes the norm, and norms do not motivate people to work better.

Vroom, on the other hand, “argued that employees tend to rationally evaluate various on-the-job work behaviours, choosing those they believe will lead to their most valued work-related rewards and outcomes.” (Navarro, 2024, p.65) Based on *Vroom's theory*, a monetary reward will only be effective if it is important and attractive enough for the employee, and at the same time, they believe they can achieve it. From the scenario, it appears that most employees, either because they worked in regions with lower turnover than others or because the reward system was too complicated, did not believe they could obtain the reward. This certainly did not help with their motivation.

As we are analysing a purely theoretical situation and the scenario lacks key information to determine what reward system would bring higher levels of employee motivation, I can only say that a more individual and personalised approach should lead to better results.

In this section, I originally suggested various personalised ideas for improving the company's bonus structure, like offering extra training as a reward or creating opportunities for promotion, while also trying to make the system simpler and fairer. However, as I kept working on this report, I felt less confident about these suggestions. Many of them seemed unrealistic or hard to implement in practice, and over time, my perspective on the whole issue shifted. I decided to present my final recommendations for changes to the bonus system in chapter A7: Change Management, where I feel they fit better.

People are not all the same. Their goals and the methods that motivate them may differ depending on their current sociological situation. Therefore, I believe having good knowledge of your employees and a personalised motivation system would bring the best results, which I will discuss in more detail later in this report.

A2: Management and Leadership Styles

The scenario under examination provides limited information about Jordan, making it difficult to determine whether he performs all ten functions described by *Mintzberg*, as referenced (Mullins, 2010, p.438). However, I will attempt to extract information from the case study below and relate it to at least some of the functions described by *Mintzberg*.

We can say that he performs the “Figurehead” role by submitting monthly reports to *Medire*. However, Ethon took away the “Leader” role from him, who decided on the bonus structure. Having led his team for the last few years, it seems that, despite knowing this structure does not work, he only recently decided to try to implement changes, which could be considered as performing the “Liaison” role. These roles are called “Interpersonal” roles by *Mintzberg*.

The next group consists of “Informational” roles, including “Monitor”, “Disseminator”, and “Spokesperson”, which involve collecting, processing, and distributing information. Reporting to *Medire* consists of collecting data from his sales representatives, processing it, and distributing it. Collecting information about his staff’s motivation levels, working on a new bonus structure, and planning to present it at the meeting next week can also be considered as a part of performing the “Informational” roles.

Similarly, the last group, “Decisional” roles, include the “Entrepreneurial” role, which Jordan fulfils by attempting to initiate changes to the bonus structure. He also plays the “Resource Allocator” role by wanting to use the entire bonus budget for the crew, and he will fulfil the “Negotiator” role at a future meeting, where he will try to convince Ethon to introduce the new bonus system.

Regarding *McGregor’s Theories X and Y*, it can be concluded that the company is more inclined towards *Theory X*, where people generally do not like working. This is why they set goals of 120-140 monthly visits and a specific visit procedure. According to *Theory X*, managers should apply strict control, and they set such a goal for themselves – monthly visits to all points – which is not always achieved. Additionally, relying on the self-assessment of sales representatives aligns with *Theory X*. Furthermore, I did not see any information in the

scenario about employees having opportunities to be creative or motivated. There is no mention of them being able to use their talents or having the chance to develop.

We also cannot say with 100% certainty what type of leader Jordan is. Both (Mullins, 2010, p.461) and (Molloy, 1998, p.4) mention *Blake and Mouton's theory*, which describes different leadership styles based on two main axes:

1. Concern for People – how much leaders care about their employees' well-being, needs, and development.
2. Concern for Production – how much the leader focuses on efficiency and work results.

Is it not true that companies' primary goal has always been profit, and employees are just a tool needed to achieve this goal? Isn't it true that management is required when the company grows so much that its founder can no longer manage it alone and is forced to hire people to help? It seems that the natural goal of every leader who is part of the management team is to focus on efficiency and work results. Every wise manager knows that without satisfied employees, they cannot achieve this goal alone. I believe Jordan, like any manager who leads employees, should focus equally on people and production. Even *Handy* said companies should balance profit with care for employees and society. This shows the need for leaders to focus on both people and production. I will examine these ideas more closely in *Chapter A5: Corporate Responsibility and Ethics*.

In terms of *Situational Leadership models*, based on the scenario, it seems that Jordan has a well-trained team that, due to limited competence and an incorrect bonus structure, has become demotivated. Based on (Mullins, 2010, p.389), where he explains *Hersey and Blanchard's theory*, as I mentioned earlier, *Jordan has an experienced team of sales representatives who need more supportive behaviour from him to increase their motivation while giving them more independence*. Therefore, Jordan should choose the "Participating (S3) leadership style" – offering much support but less management, as the employees are competent but need motivation.

A3: Group and Team Effectiveness

In this chapter, I would like to evaluate the effectiveness of the sales “team” by using the *Factors Affecting Performance model* and supporting my analysis with theories about groups and teams. To do this, I first define a “group” and a “team”.

Many people have explored groups and teams in the context of management. However, I could not find a single person who defines “group” and “team”. One of the most frequently cited figures in this context is *George Homans*, who describes a “group” based on the interactions between its members. According to *Homans*, a “group” is a „number of persons who communicate with one another often over a span of time, and who are few enough so that each person can communicate with all the others, not at secondhand”(Homans, 2009, p.38). Members of a “group” share common beliefs and values, and, over time, a leader tends to emerge naturally, someone who accepts the “group” norms and demonstrates the ability to coordinate the activities of its members.

Robbins and Judge define a “group” „as two or more individuals, interacting and interdependent, who have come together to achieve particular objectives”(Robbins and Judge, 2013, p.272). They emphasise the concept of purpose as the key factor that holds a “group” together.

J. Richard Hackman states at the outset that „we are relaxed about terminology. Throughout this book, we use the terms group and team completely interchangeably”(Hackman, 1990, p.14). He also clearly outlines the key characteristics of a group (Hackman, 1990, p.4):

- It is possible to clearly define who is a member of the “group” and who is not, even if membership changes.
- The “group” exists to accomplish a specific task for which members share responsibility.
- “Groups” operate within a specific organisational context.

(Katzenbach and Smith, 2003, chap.3).

From this detailed yet somewhat unnecessary introduction, which aimed to clearly define the differences between the concepts of “groups” and “teams” and outline their characteristics, it becomes evident that, depending on the author, both concepts often have similar meanings. It seems that the term “group” is more commonly used in informal contexts, while “team” refers to a collection of employees within a company who:

- 1. Have a common goal:** In our case, the seven sales representatives selling *Medire* products.
- 2. Share responsibility for results:** *Drug Sales Ltd.* divided Ireland into seven regions, with each sales representative assigned one area. This structure created seven separate, one-person workgroups responsible for sales in their designated area. While they share the same overarching goal, each representative is responsible for maintaining their respective region.
- 3. Interdependence and interaction:** As mentioned earlier, because *Drug Sales Ltd.* has assigned seven regions with individual responsibility, the interdependence and interaction between sales representatives may be limited.
- 4. Complementary skills:** Teams are usually composed of people with diverse skills that complement each other, which is in line with *Belbin’s team roles* (Mullins, 2010, p.342):

Roles and descriptions – team-role contribution**Allowable weaknesses**

	Roles and descriptions – team-role contribution	Allowable weaknesses
Plant	Creative, imaginative, unorthodox. Solves difficult problems.	Ignores details. Too preoccupied to communicate effectively.
Resource investigator	Extravert, enthusiastic, and communicative. Explores opportunities. Develops contacts.	Over-optimistic. Loses interest once initial enthusiasm has passed.
Co-ordinator	Mature, confident, a good chairperson. Clarifies goals and promotes decision-making. Delegates well.	It can be seen as manipulative. Offloads personal work.
Shaper	Challenging, dynamic, thrives on pressure. Has the drive and courage to overcome obstacles.	Can provoke others. Hurts people's feelings.
Monitor-Evaluator	Sober, strategic and discerning. Sees all options. Judges accurately.	Lacks drive and ability to inspire others.
Teamworker	Co-operative, mild, perceptive and diplomatic. Listens, builds, averts friction.	Indecisive in crunch situations.
Implementer	Disciplined, reliable, conservative and efficient. Turns ideas into practical actions.	Somewhat inflexible. Slow to respond to new possibilities.
Completer	Painstaking, conscientious, anxious. Searches out errors and omissions. Delivers on time.	Inclined to worry unduly. Reluctant to delegate.
Specialist	Single-minded, self-sharing, dedicated. Provides knowledge and skills in rare supply.	Contributes on only a narrow front. Dwells on technicalities.

Table 1: (Mullins, 2010, p.343)

In formal groups created by the company, group members are often selected based on pre-defined characteristics and skills. Although the scenario does not explicitly state this, as mentioned earlier, *Drug Sales Ltd.* divided Ireland into seven areas, each individually managed by one of the seven experienced sales representatives. I believe that these sales representatives were chosen based on specific characteristics and skills suited for the role. Since each representative works independently within their region, their interaction and the opportunity to complement each other with missing skills are limited.

- 5. Common approach:** Teams develop shared working methods and rules of cooperation that help achieve their goals. In the case of formalised groups, these methods and rules may be based on established procedures and guidelines that have been put in place beforehand.

For obvious reasons, informal and formal groups differ in several ways. For example, formal groups created in a company usually have a leader who is their superior. The same happens when setting goals and choosing group members. Goals should be clearly defined, and members should be selected so that their skills complement each other and help achieve the goal.

Based on my analysis, the seven sales representatives working under *Jordan Blake's* leadership at *Drug Sales Ltd.* could structurally be considered a team. However, considering my earlier explanation of groups within a company, I would argue that these seven sales representatives function more like seven individual workgroups.

(Mullins, 2010, p.318). The “forming” stage is when the group is created, and members get to know each other and set goals. Since the group has been together for some time, they have passed this stage. The next stage, “storming”, involves conflicts arising from differences in opinions, work styles, or priorities. However, this stage is unlikely because each member works independently in their regions, with minimal interaction. The third stage, “norming”, happens when the group works harmoniously and establishes clear cooperation rules. The next stage, “performing”, is when the group becomes highly efficient and focuses on achieving goals. Finally, “adjourning” is when the group completes its tasks and disbands.

Blake's group may be in the "norming" or "performing" stages, where they function harmoniously, with each member accepting their role and working toward their goals. However, as I mentioned earlier, since each sales representative works independently in their region, this assumption might not fully apply. It is similar to the Irish team at the Olympics – they represent the same country, but each athlete competes individually without working together.

Therefore, my initial attempt to evaluate the sales "team" effectiveness using the *Factors Affecting Performance model*, supported by theories on groups and teams, is not entirely possible. The effectiveness of a group can only be measured when its members work together toward a shared goal, sharing tasks and responsibilities. Each sales representative works independently in their region, so there is no evident interdependence in completing tasks. The goal may be shared, but the implementation is individual.

From the perspective of the group I described above, the sales representatives do not meet the requirements. They are more like a collection of independent units with the same organisational goal but operating independently.

Jordan Blake, as the leader of this group, may act as a coordinator or mentor, but this does not mean he is creating an effective group in the sense of team cooperation.

This conclusion does not stop me from using Fred's (Nickols, 2016) *Factors Affecting Performance* to highlight seven key factors influencing individual performance in the workplace. These factors can help assess *Blake* and his team:

- 1. Goal Clarity:** Employees must have clear goals to achieve desired results. Tracking progress or knowing when tasks are complete is hard without clear goals. This concept is linked to *Vroom's Expectancy Theory*, which suggests that well-defined goals motivate employees. In our case, *Blake* works to motivate his team and meet *Medire's* expectations. He uses a bonus system aligned with *Medire's* goals, but the complexity of the bonus system and negative perceptions about it may reduce motivation and performance.

- 2. Repertoire:** Achieving a goal requires employees to have the right skills, knowledge, and behaviours to adapt to changing conditions and overcome obstacles. Depending on the situation, this may involve performing routine tasks, improvising, and finding new solutions.

This point aligns with *Belbin's team roles theory*, highlighting that each team member brings different skills and characteristics, enabling the group to complete tasks in various situations effectively.

The case does not specify the characteristics of the team, except for the statement that *Drug Sales Ltd.* "offers a comprehensive "turnkey" sales force that includes ... training" (Nicell, 2024). This suggests that the team may be well-selected with the right skills and knowledge to achieve their sales goals independently.

- 3. Knowledge of Structures:** To work effectively, employees must understand the structure of their situation, including the interconnections and dependencies. This allows them to choose the correct methods to achieve their goals.

The *Johari Window model* helps people understand their relationships and uncover hidden aspects of situations and actions, which supports the understanding of team or organisational structures. In *Theory X and Y*, the work environment is shaped by the type of management in place.

Blake and the board created a clear organisational structure, including mechanisms to control employees and a detailed procedure for visiting pharmacies. This information clearly defines the goals and responsibilities of *Blake's team*. On the other hand, the unclear conditions of the bonus structure, even in a perfectly designed work environment, will not improve the motivation or productivity of the team.

- 4. Feedback:** This is essential for assessing progress and correcting corrections. It allows employees to compare their actions with the intended goal and adjust their behaviour accordingly.

Feedback is a key element of the *Johari Window* because it helps discover “blind spots” in communication, allowing individuals to adjust their actions based on input from others. As *Tuckman* describes, feedback is critical in the “storming” and “norming” phases of group development. During these phases, teams learn from mistakes and improve their cooperation.

Jordan Blake wants to change the bonus system based on feedback from both the client and his team. They have reported that the current bonus system does not meet expectations, is inconsistent with the client’s goals, and leaves the team demotivated due to unclear information on how the bonus is distributed.

- 5. Mental Models:** Employees often rely on mental models in the absence of feedback – internal beliefs about what is appropriate and effective. *Fred* suggests analysing these mental models to identify misconceptions and promote effective ones.

In *Tuckman’s stages of group development*, teams create shared mental models that enable coordinated action. Based on *Mintzberg’s roles*, *Blake* should be able to supervise the development of these models and, through observation, promote the desired ones while addressing incorrect ones, such as when “he also noticed that ... more stores than ever had a perfect planogram ... he was concerned that representatives might be fabricating data.” (Nicell, 2024).

- 6. Motivation:** Besides skills and knowledge, motivation is a key factor influencing performance. Employees must be motivated to perform their tasks and strive to achieve goals. *Fred* distinguishes between two primary sources of motivation: job satisfaction and external incentives like bonuses or promotions.

This is reflected in *Herzberg’s two-factor theory*, which divides motivators into hygiene factors (e.g., work environment) and internal motivators (e.g., recognition and achievements), which directly impact what drives employees to act.

The case presents three failed bonus structure concepts. It indicates that *Jordan Blake* is preparing a new structure to meet customer expectations and improve the sales team's low motivation.

7. Environment: Even with the abovementioned factors, performance can be hindered by an unfavourable work environment. *Fred* lists factors like a lack of tools and equipment, competing priorities, and a lousy work atmosphere. The work environment must be supportive and conducive to goal achievement for employees to perform effectively.

A favourable work environment results from a management style that is both people-oriented and task-oriented, which aligns with *Blake and Mouton's Management Grid*. In *Herzberg's theory*, hygiene factors such as working conditions and workplace relationships are key to creating a favourable environment.

From the Case, it can be concluded that the company focuses on generating revenue for its customers, and sales representatives may be overloaded with tasks: "between 200 to 300 stores each ... with encouragement to exceed this target by reaching out to 140 stores monthly" (Nicell, 2024). The company also uses iPads to record sales representatives' visits and activities in detail, which can create a sense of constant surveillance. These factors, combined with frequent changes to the bonus system, indicate issues with its effectiveness and alignment with the realities of the work and do not seem to create an environment conducive to increasing work efficiency.

In summary, the analysis of *Drug Sales Ltd.* in the context of *Fred Nickols' model* highlights several significant issues affecting individual performance. The primary factors reducing motivation and efficiency are the lack of clear communication among sales representatives, an inappropriate organisational structure, an ineffective bonus system, and a stressful work environment. The centralised decision-making model, overload of responsibilities, and lack of investment in employee development lead to frustration, demotivation, and disengagement. These conclusions suggest an urgent need to reorganise the structure of *Jordan's team* and improve internal processes, including the motivation system and employee support so that the company can effectively compete in the OTC market.

A4: Organisational Structure

In this chapter, I will attempt to diagnose and, if possible, describe any structural issues within *Drug Sales Ltd.*, mainly using *Urwick's Principles of Organisation*. To do so, it is first necessary to define organisational structure and its characteristics and types.

An organisational structure is a planned and coordinated system that defines how tasks are formally divided, grouped, and coordinated within an organisation (Robbins and Judge, 2013, p.480). It defines who is responsible for what, to whom individual employees report, and how information flows within the company. Organisational structure can exist independently of specific individuals and is often presented graphically in the form of an organisational chart (Mullins, 2010, pt.5). In this case, we will present only a small part of the structure of *Drug Sales Ltd.*, as shown in the diagram below:

Diagram 1: Fragment of the Organizational Structure of *Drug Sales Ltd.*

In addition, „managers need to address six key elements when they design their organization’s structure:” (Robbins and Judge, 2013, p.480)

(Burns and Stalker, 1994) in his book *The Management of Innovation* proposes a division into mechanical and organic structures. The mechanistic structure is appropriate for stable market

and technological conditions, while the organic structure is an organisational model more suitable for rapidly changing market and technological conditions. Below are the main differences between the mechanistic and organic structures:

Characteristics	Mechanistic Structure	Organic Structure
Hierarchy	Rigid, with many levels	Flat, with fewer levels
Task Division	Narrow specialisation, rigid roles	Flexible roles, teamwork
Communication	Formal, top-down	Open, multi-directional
Authority	Centralised at the top	Decentralised
Decision Making	Centralised	Decentralised
Focus	Obedience, loyalty	Knowledge, competencies
Adaptability	Low	High

Table 2: Comparison of mechanistic and organic structure

Alfred Chandler, in his book *Strategy and Structure* introduces division into functional and divisional structures. As (Awa, 2016) explains, employees are grouped according to their specialisations or functions in a functional structure. Examples of departments in such a structure include production/operations, finance/accounting or marketing. In contrast, a divisional structure divides the company into smaller units called divisions. These divisions can be created based on geographical, product, or customer-type criteria. Each division has some autonomy and its functional departments.

The divisions above describe different aspects of organisational structure as follows:

1. **Simple, bureaucratic, and matrix** refer to the level of complexity and formalisation within the organisation.
2. **Mechanistic and organic structures** focus on flexibility and methods of operation (rigid procedures vs. adaptability).
3. **Functional and divisional structures** describe how work and responsibilities are divided (by function or product/region).

Consequently, these structures can overlap, meaning that a simple structure may exhibit characteristics of both a mechanistic and a functional structure. A bureaucracy can be either

mechanistic or organic, depending on its level of flexibility. In contrast, a matrix structure often combines functional and divisional aspects, making it more organic.

As we can read in the case, „*Drug Sales Ltd.* operates as a contract sales organisation for pharmaceutical firms” (Nicell, 2024), and we are focusing only on the part of *Drug Sales Ltd.* that deals with servicing *Medire*. The company has divided its structure into regions, with each region responsible for servicing pharmacies within its area, which indicates that *Drug Sales Ltd.* operates with a divisional structure. Moreover, the company uses formal procedures, strictly defined roles, and a strong hierarchy – evidenced by the system for managing sales representatives’ visits, the requirement for a certain number of visits, maintaining documentation on iPads, evaluating planograms, and the hierarchical reporting of results by *Jordan Blake* to headquarters. These elements demonstrate that *Drug Sales Ltd.* follows a mechanistic structure. Additionally, we are only examining a small portion of the organisation, which suggests that it is part of a larger company where the formalisation of processes, procedures, and hierarchy is essential for managing a large number of resources and activities. These factors point to the organisation having a bureaucratic structure.

(Mullins, 2010) indicates that the choice of organisational structure should be adapted to, among other things, the organisation's strategy, size, culture and environment. In the same vein (Drucker, 1954), „a good organisation structure is not a panacea ... But the right organisation structure is the necessary foundation; without it, the best performance in all other areas of management will be ineffectual and frustrated”, which means that while a well-designed structure does not automatically ensure success, its absence or a poorly chosen structure can effectively prevent it. That is why it is so important for the organisational structure to align with the company’s specifics and support the implementation of its strategy and goals. In practice, however, it seems that many companies naturally adopt a structure that reflects their characteristics and operational specifics. As a result, the organisational structure reflects the company’s strategy, culture, and the environment in which it operates. Both organisational and market needs shape its elements. In the case of *Drug Sales Ltd.*, the divisional and mechanistic structure is primarily a result of its operational specifics, including regional service and the need to maintain formal procedures and hierarchy to manage processes effectively.

To further assess the organisational structure of *Drug Sales Ltd.*, it is helpful to apply *Urwick's Principles of Organization*, which provide a set of universal guidelines for analysing and designing effective organisational structures. According to (Mullins, 2010, p.561), the following principles of organisation are distinguished:

1. The principle of the objective

“The organisation should only exist in order to carry out some specific purpose implicit in the forecast and the plan. Every piece of it should make a definite and authorised contribution to that purpose. Otherwise there is no reason for its existence.”(Urwick, 1947, p.42)

Every organisation needs a clear, well-defined goal, with all its activities directed towards achieving it. Without a common goal, efforts become fragmented, leading to inefficiency and chaos.

Drug Sales Ltd. changed its bonus system twice in the first three months of its collaboration with *Medire*. This reflects a lack of clearly defined goals and expectations for the work of sales representatives. „The shift away from sales in the bonus structure raised concerns about whether the representatives were still attempting to sell products in stores”(Nicell, 2024), which could hinder the company's primary objective of “generate revenue at a lower expense than if the client maintained an in-house sales team.” (Nicell, 2024)

2. The principle of specialisation

„The work of every person in the organisation should be confined as far as possible to the performance of a single leading function.”(Urwick, 1947, p.48)

Work in the organisation should be divided into specialised tasks that are appropriately assigned to employees depending on their competencies and skills.

In Drug Sales Ltd., a division exists, a group of sales representatives is assigned to individual regions serving their customers by supplying them with *Medire* products. On the other hand, supplying is not everything. Additional tasks of sales representatives include minimising off-sale time, directing contact with pharmacists and brand promotion among store employees, taking care of promotional displays, and reporting data on visits. In addition, limited interaction between sales representatives caused by the division of work by location can lead to difficulties in exchanging experiences in the group. Additionally, competition between sales representatives caused by an incorrect bonus structure can lead to focusing on regional results at the expense of cooperation and the good of the company as a whole.

3. The principle of coordination

“The purpose of all organisation is to unify effort—that is, co-ordination.”(Urwick, 1947, p.43)

All activities in the organisation should be harmoniously coordinated to achieve the company's goals collectively. Coordination involves ensuring cooperation between different departments, employees, and functions to avoid conflicts, duplication of work, or waste of resources. This allows the organisation to operate as a cohesive whole.

The lack of clearly defined goals makes it difficult to coordinate activities because employees are unsure of what they should focus on and what results are expected. A poorly designed bonus system leads to abuses and motivates representatives to focus on tasks inconsistent with the organisation's objectives.

4. The principle of authority

“Authority is the right to give orders and the power to exact obedience.”(Henri Fayol, 1949, p.21)

Power is defined as the right to demand that others perform specific actions. The existence of an organisation depends on the presence of power, as it provides direction for actions and ensures order.

The bonus system, which relies on the declarations of sales representatives, points to a lack of adequate tools for controlling their work. A lack of control is synonymous with a lack of power. *Blake* has no authority over the system to monitor and verify his team's actions, leading to the abuse and demotivation of honest employees.

5. The principle of responsibility

“Any individual or group to whom is assigned authority for which he is or they are not held accountable to someone will tend to exercise that authority with decreasing effectiveness.”(Urwick, 1947, p.45)

Every person with authority in the organisation is responsible for the results of their actions. Responsibility is inextricably linked to the scope of duties and the authority assigned. The greater the authority, the greater the responsibility.

A bonus system based on the declarations of sales representatives, without appropriate verification mechanisms, led to abuses. The lack of an effective control system indicates negligence in the responsibility for monitoring the work of subordinates.

6. The principle of definition

“The content of each position, both the duties involved, the authority and responsibility contemplated and the relationships with other positions should be clearly defined in writing and published to all concerned.”(Mullins, 2010, p.562)

Every organisational function, duty, and responsibility should be clearly defined, understandable, and documented. This ensures that every employee knows their responsibilities, eliminating misunderstandings and increasing efficiency. Clarity in defining roles and tasks allows for better cooperation and prevents overlapping duties.

The lack of clearly defined rules in the bonus structure led to frustration, demotivation, and misunderstandings. On the other hand, all sales reps' procedures are clearly set.

7. The principle of correspondence

“Any individual or group to whom is assigned authority for which he is or they are not held accountable to someone will tend to exercise that authority with decreasing effectiveness.”(Urwick, 1947, p.45)

Authority gives the employee the right to make decisions, while responsibility involves being accountable for the results of those decisions. A proper balance between authority and responsibility is essential for effectively managing one's work. Unlike the principle of responsibility, this principle applies to all employees. Each person performing a task should take responsibility for it.

The lack of a clearly defined scope of responsibility for actual sales results and a bonus system based on the number of pharmacy visits can lead sales representatives to focus on quantity rather than the quality of interactions. This is not aligned with the goals of *Drug Sales Ltd.* and *Medire*.

8. The principle of span of control

„No superior can supervise directly the work of more than five or, at the most, six subordinates whose work interlocks.”(Urwick, 1947, p.52)

Managers can effectively supervise only a limited number of subordinates. When the number of people reporting to one manager becomes too large, it can result in communication issues, challenges in supervision, and difficulties in maintaining control over the team.

In the case of *Drug Sales Ltd.*, the issue of inadequate supervision is caused by different factors.

9. The principle of balance

“Each portion and function of an enterprise should operate with equal effectiveness in making its allotted contribution to the total purpose.”(Urwick, 1947, p.121)

Maintaining the right balance between various elements of an organisation – such as power, responsibility, authority, and the hierarchical structure – ensures its efficient and effective functioning. The goal is to create a stable and effective organisational framework where no department dominates the others, and all elements work together towards achieving common objectives.

In the case of *Drug Sales Ltd.*, the lack of balance in the bonus structure, which initially focused solely on sales results, became problematic. In the OCT market, clients like *Medire* expect sales representatives to generate orders, build brand image, and educate pharmacists. This shift led to the company moving away from emphasising sales results. The combination of poorly defined tasks, lack of control over task execution, absence of accountability for results, and a bonus system that encourages competition between regions rather than cooperation weakened the team's effectiveness. It undermined the organisation's ability to achieve its goals cohesively.

10. The principle of continuity

„Apart from the effect on the existing situation, there is an important subsidiary principle applicable to organisation as a whole which makes it an imperative responsibility of the administrator that he should have a plan.”(Urwick, 1947, p.39)

Organisational development and adaptation is a continuous process. The organisation should not be seen as a static entity but as a dynamic system that must evolve to meet changing environmental conditions and internal needs. Changes in the organisation – such as adjustments to structure, procedures, management, or goals – should occur harmoniously and gradually to avoid disruptions in its functioning.

The instability of the bonus system, where the last version remained in place for too long despite its known imperfections, and the failure to adapt quickly to the specific needs of the OCT market suggests a lack of organisational flexibility. This inability to respond rapidly to changing market conditions can lead to lower employee motivation, a loss of competitiveness, and difficulties achieving the organisation's long-term goals.

Based on the presented conclusions, it can be concluded that the unstable and poorly designed bonus system at *Drug Sales Ltd.* significantly impacts the organisation's efficiency and employee motivation. Frequent changes to the bonus system in a short period suggest a lack of clearly defined goals and expectations from the sales representatives, making it difficult for them to focus on achieving the company's main objectives, such as "generating revenue at a lower expense than if the client maintained an in-house sales team" (Nicell, 2024).

Additionally, the improper division of roles and tasks and insufficient interaction between sales representatives fosters competition instead of cooperation, undermining organisational goals' achievement. The absence of clearly defined objectives and an effective monitoring system contributed to employee abuse and demotivation. Specifically, based on the declarations of sales representatives without proper verification mechanisms, the bonus system resulted in a lack of accountability and oversight, leading to misunderstandings and frustration within the team.

Moreover, the instability of the bonus system, which did not adapt to the specifics of the OCT market, indicates a lack of organisational flexibility. This made it challenging to respond swiftly to changing market needs, potentially reducing competitiveness and hindering achieving long-term goals.

All these factors lead to the conclusion that the absence of balance in the bonus system, poorly defined goals and tasks, and insufficient supervision and control over performance have a negative impact on team cooperation, organisational efficiency, and the achievement of the company's main objectives.

A5: Corporate Responsibility and Ethics

In this chapter, I will analyse the management of the sales function in the context of three main approaches to organisational purpose: *profit maximisation* as defined by *Milton Friedman*, *stakeholder theory* as proposed by *Charles Handy*, and the concept of *new capitalists* as outlined by *Davis, Lukommik, and Watson*. The aim is to evaluate which of these approaches best represents the management of the sales function at *Drug Sales Ltd.* and to propose possible improvements using ethical theories such as *John Stuart Mill's utilitarianism*, *Immanuel Kant's categorical imperative*, and the *concept of justice* as interpreted by *Plato* and *Rawls*.

To achieve this, the first step is to define the scope of the sales function and identify its key aspects. Sales management involves planning, organising, directing, and controlling activities related to selling a company's products or services. The primary objective is maximising revenue and sales efficiency while ensuring customer satisfaction and alignment with the organisation's goals.

The management of the sales function includes:

1. Sales planning involves defining sales goals, strategies, and methods for reaching customers. This process may include market analysis, customer segmentation, and developing sales plans. Unfortunately, our scenario lacks such information.
2. Recruitment and training of the sales team involve selecting the right employees to achieve sales goals and preparing them for effective sales through proper development. In our scenario, *Drug Sales Ltd.* "offers a comprehensive 'turnkey' sales force that includes recruiting and training" (Nicell, 2024).
3. Motivation and remuneration involve creating an appropriate compensation system that motivates the team to achieve set goals. This may also include recognising employees' achievements or providing additional training. From the scenario, we know that *Drug Sales Ltd.* has faced challenges with this aspect since the beginning of its cooperation with *Medire*.

4. Results control involves monitoring the effectiveness of sales activities, analysing sales results, and comparing them with established goals. In this case, however, we do not have enough information. We are unaware of the specific goals and current results, the method used by *Medire* and *Drug Sales Ltd.* to measure the effectiveness of sales representatives, and most importantly, the effectiveness results are reported by the sales representatives themselves. This self-reporting is potentially biased and may lead to erroneous conclusions, as no independent system verifies the data.
5. Customer Relationships involve managing customer relationships, building long-term connections, providing high-quality service, and maintaining customer loyalty. *Medire* requires this from *Drug Sales Ltd.*, and both *Drug Sales Ltd.* and *Jordan Blake* know its importance. However, due to a poorly designed bonus system for the sales team, fostering strong customer relationships is not necessarily their primary goal.

Proper management of the sales function is therefore crucial to the success of *Drug Sales Ltd.*, as without effective sales, there is no revenue, which negatively impacts the organisation's further development. As we can conclude from this brief analysis, the current model of managing the sales function at *Drug Sales Ltd.* is ineffective and requires significant improvements in planning, team motivation, and performance control. These changes are necessary to meet *Medire's* expectations and ensure the company's long-term success.

Managing the sales function and aligning it with key organisational values, such as maximising profits or building relationships with stakeholders, is fundamental to the success of any company. In the context of *Drug Sales Ltd.*, it is worth examining three different theories:

Milton Friedman, a Nobel Prize-winning economist, argued that the only social responsibility of business is to increase its profits. "He did not believe that company leaders had any social responsibility" (Schroeder, 2002, p.260). *Friedman* maintained that businesses should focus solely on generating shareholder value rather than engaging in philanthropy or other activities that do not directly contribute to increasing profits.

Charles (Handy, 1998), in his book *The Hungry Spirit: Beyond Capitalism: A Quest for Purpose in the Modern World*, presents the concept of an organisation in the shape of a three-leaf clover, known as the "shamrock organisation". According to this concept, each leaf of the

clover represents a different group of people who make up the organisation: the professional core, the contractual environment, and the flexible workforce. *Handy's* concept asserts that the organisation should act not only in the interest of owners or shareholders but also in the interest of employees, customers, suppliers, and the community. He emphasises cooperation and social responsibility, believing that the company's success depends on balancing the needs of all stakeholders rather than focusing solely on maximising profits.

On the other hand, (Davis *et al.*, 2006), in their book *The New Capitalists: How Citizen Investors Are Reshaping the Corporate Agenda*, describe the concept of *new capitalists*. These are the millions of citizen investors who, through their pension and investment funds, have become owners of global corporations. This shift represents a change in enterprises' ownership structure and highlights citizen investors' growing influence on corporate management.

To sum up the three concepts above – *profit maximisation* according to *Friedman*, *Handy's stakeholder theory*, and the ideas of the *new capitalists* from *Davis*, *Lukommik*, and *Watson* – in my understanding, they lead to a common denominator: the key goal of business activity remains generating profits for the owners. Socially responsible activities, philanthropy, or cooperation with employees and contractors are motivated by pragmatism, not altruism. Companies engage in such initiatives not out of the “goodness of their hearts” but from the desire to achieve image benefits, increase employee loyalty, or acquire new customers, which ultimately translates into higher revenues. In this light, the differences between the discussed theories mainly result from the perspective on stakeholders. However, in practice, each model boils down to calculating profits and losses and protecting the owners' interests.

In the case of *Drug Sales Ltd.*, we see some contradictions that make it difficult to classify the company. On the one hand, the company declares its care for the customer's needs – *Medire* – and tries to adapt to their expectations, for example, by modifying the bonus system for sales representatives. On the other hand, “the company assures its clients that their sales representatives will generate revenue at a lower expense than if the client maintained an in-house sales team” (Nicell, 2024), which indicates an approach focused mainly on profit, more in line with *Friedman's* concept.

Ultimately, suppose Drug Sales Ltd. meets *Medire's* expectations and extends the contract. In that case, the company will satisfy its customers' needs while generating a profit and ensuring continued business. This brings us back to my earlier conclusion that the three concepts above ultimately lead to the same goal of generating profit for the owners.

My original intention for this chapter was to assess which of the above approaches best characterises the way the sales function is managed at *Drug Sales Ltd.* and to suggest possible improvements based on ethical theories such as *John Stuart Mill's utilitarianism*, *Immanuel Kant's categorical imperative*, and the *concept of justice* as interpreted by *Plato* and *Rawls*.

However, finding clear answers to ethical or existential questions or deciding if ethical theories are completely valid seems impossible. This is because moral principles need to be the same for everyone, which is unrealistic. Everyone is different, and unique experiences shape each person's life. Even the most minor event, in the context of previous experiences and future consequences, can radically change the perception of specific issues. Therefore, a universal approach to ethics remains challenging, and morality is dynamic and subjective, requiring constant adaptation to an ever-changing reality.

My analysis suggests that *Mill's utilitarianism* aligns with *Handy's* more practical theory, which focuses on the consequences of actions and the principle that the greatest happiness for the most significant number is the highest moral goal. This could be applied to create a more effective and equitable incentive system that benefits employees and customers.

In turn, *Kant's categorical imperative*, with which I am afraid I have to disagree due to its assertion that rationalism allows for the assessment of the universality of principles, could still help define company conduct rules that align with universal moral standards, thereby eliminating unethical practices, such as data manipulation. Although I understand the idea, I remain unconvinced by it.

Plato's concept of justice, which emphasises harmony and order in society and the individual, can also be compared to *Handy's* theory in business terms. This approach could be used to create a more balanced work environment that considers the needs of all stakeholders, thereby increasing their commitment and loyalty to the company.

In summary, my conclusions about Corporate Responsibility and Ethics do not differ significantly from the ideas I had before delving into this topic. This aligns with a logical and natural understanding of organisational management.

It is also worth mentioning the *Kraljic Matrix*, a tool used to manage purchasing and classify suppliers based on their strategic importance and market risk. This matrix allows for adapting approaches to different purchasing categories. This mirrors my conclusion: depending on the context and various factors, the approach to a particular stakeholder – whether employee, customer, or supplier – should be flexible to ensure optimal results. Like my conclusion, this practical solution highlights the need for flexibility and pragmatism in management.

A6: Organisational Culture

This chapter aims to analyse the organisational culture of *Drug Sales Ltd.* by creating a *Cultural Web*, which will help identify key elements of this culture and assess their impact on the organisation's functioning. Based on this analysis, the strengths and weaknesses that may significantly affect the company's efficiency and future development will be highlighted.

However, the first step of this chapter is to define organisational culture. To do this, we should begin by defining the term “culture”. According to the (Cambridge Dictionary, 2024), culture is “the way of life of a particular people, especially as shown in their behaviour, habits, attitudes toward each other, and their moral and religious beliefs.” Organisational culture, on the other hand, refers to the complex set of values, beliefs, assumptions, and symbols that define how a company conducts its business. In this sense, culture has a pervasive impact on a company, as it not only defines the identity of its employees, customers, suppliers, and competitors but also shapes how the company interacts with these key entities (Barney, 1986).

Organisational culture is a dynamic process in which individuals within an organisation, while being true to themselves, influence and are shaped by others. Employees bring their values, beliefs, and experiences, which interact with the organisation's values and norms. These values and norms influence employees' behaviours, attitudes, and mindsets.

In organisational culture, we observe the mutual influence between individuals and groups. Employees can impact the company's atmosphere, the decisions made, the methods of communication, and the approach to customers. At the same time, however, the organisation – its structures, processes, and leaders – sets specific frameworks and expectations that shape the behaviour of individuals.

Both (Barney, 1986) and (Hofstede, 1983) highlight that understanding organisational culture is crucial for effective management. Perceiving the psychological climate in the workplace significantly impacts employee attitudes, motivation, and performance. Analysing organisational culture can assist managers in various ways, such as identifying the values and beliefs that guide employee actions, adapting management styles to align with the

organisational culture, and motivating employees by creating a work environment consistent with their values.

Organisational culture reflects the collective psychology of the people within a company. Psychoanalysis helps us understand their values, motivations, and needs, enabling management to adjust strategies, create a supportive work environment, and improve employee efficiency and engagement.

There are many tools and methods for analysing organisational culture. One such tool is the *Culture Web*, developed by *Johnson and Scholes* in 1987. It aims to understand how an organisation's culture influences its goals and strategies. The *Culture Web* highlights hidden assumptions and the explicit behaviours that shape an organisation's culture.

According to (*Johnson et al.*, 2005, p.202), the *Cultural Web* consists of six interrelated elements:

1. **Rituals and Routines:** The organisation's daily activities and working methods. They show "how things are done here." They can help the organisation succeed but can be hard to change.
2. **Stories:** These are tales of success, failure, heroes, and rule-breakers shared by people in the organisation. They show what the organisation sees as important.
3. **Symbols:** These include things like logos, uniforms, job titles, or office spaces. They represent what the organisation values.
4. **Power Structures:** This means who has power in the organisation and how it is shared. These people or groups often shape key decisions and activities.
5. **Control Systems:** These are the rules and tools used to check and manage how the organisation is doing. They show what the organisation cares about most.
6. **Paradigm:** This is how people in the organisation think and believe. It affects how they see the world and what goals they focus on. It is part of the culture and daily life of the organisation.

At *Drug Sales Ltd.*, routines are important in the company's daily work. For example, sales representatives use iPads to document their visits to pharmacies, showing that the company

focuses on efficiently organising work well. Employees must follow clear sales steps to keep things consistent across the company. However, if there are too many rules, it can limit flexibility. Following rules too strictly might stop employees from being creative or adapting when needed.

There is no information about stories or symbols at *Drug Sales Ltd.* in the scenario besides the company's introduction. While the introduction gives some background on the company, those are not stories shared informally between employees. Also, there is nothing about logos or images.

Drug Sales Ltd. has a power structure where the founder, *Ethan Carter*, makes most of the important decisions. This system gives him complete control but can stop employees from being creative. Decisions made at the top and not considering input from lower-level employees may not always be the best for the company.

Drug Sales Ltd.'s control system is based on sales representatives' self-assessments. This approach can lead to manipulation. Initially based solely on sales performance, the complex bonus system was modified to account for customer expectations. However, these adjustments require further refinement to effectively motivate employees to align their actions with the organisation's long-term goals.

From my above analysis, we can identify the strengths and weaknesses of Drug Sales Ltd.

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>Clearly defined procedures and rituals</p> <p>One of the main strengths of <i>Drug Sales Ltd.</i> is its strong focus on operational efficiency, which is evident in daily procedures, such as documenting sales representatives' visits to pharmacies using iPads. This type of standardised process allows for quality control of work and monitoring of sales results. Employees have clearly defined tasks, which makes it easier to track their progress and identify areas for improvement.</p>	<p>Excessive formalisation of processes</p> <p>Although the formalisation of processes in <i>Drug Sales Ltd.</i> ensures efficiency and compliance with procedures, its excess can lead to problems with the organisation's flexibility. Too rigid adherence to procedures and rules can limit employee creativity and inhibit innovation. In particular, when entering a new market such as the OCT market, excessive formalisation can be a barrier to quick response to diagnosed problems.</p>
<p>Adaptation of the bonus structure</p> <p>Initially based only on sales results, the bonus system was modified also to consider customer expectations. This type of flexibility in adapting the motivation system is beneficial because it allows for a better understanding and satisfaction of the organisation's long-term needs and increases employee engagement.</p>	<p>Low decentralisation of decisions</p> <p>Although centralisation can be an asset in the initial development phase of the company, in the long run, it can lead to limitations in innovation and employee engagement. The lack of participation of lower levels in decision-making can cause frustration among employees who feel ignored and have no influence on the company's development. In particular, as the company grows, it will be necessary to delegate more responsibility to the middle management level to enable better adaptation to changing market conditions.</p> <p>Problems with motivation</p> <p>The bonus system, although modified, still requires further changes. Although it considers customer expectations, it is not balanced enough to effectively motivate employees to act towards the organisation's long-term goals.</p>

Table 3: Strengths and Weaknesses of Drug Sales Ltd. based on the Cultural Web

In conclusion, *Drug Sales Ltd.*'s organisational culture presents strengths and weaknesses that significantly impact its effectiveness. On the one hand, the strong formalisation of processes and centralisation of authority provide order and predictability. On the other hand, they restrict flexibility, innovation, and employee engagement. As the company enters the new OCT market, adapting the culture to meet new challenges and evolving circumstances will be crucial.

A7: Change Management

Change in an organisation is essential, especially when the goal is to improve performance and solve existing problems. In this chapter, I will analyse the change management process based on two key models: *Lewin's theory* and *Kotter's eight-step model*. I will focus on how *Jordan* can successfully implement a new reward structure and eliminate the difficulties of organising and managing his group. From the article by (Cummings *et al.*, 2016) entitled *Unfreezing Change as Three Steps: Rethinking Kurt Lewin's Legacy for Change Management*, we learn that *Kurt Lewin's theory* of change is a simple but effective model that describes the process of implementing change in an organisation. It consists of three stages:

1. **Unfreeze:** Preparing the organisation for change by questioning current practices, creating a sense of urgency, and overcoming resistance. Employees must understand why change is necessary.
2. **Change:** Implementing new processes, structures, or behaviours. At this stage, effective communication, support, and buy-in from all parties are essential.
3. **Refreeze:** Consolidating the changes to ensure they become part of the organisation's daily operations. Stabilisation is key to preventing a return to old habits.

Lewin's model provides a solid foundation for understanding the dynamics of change and highlights the importance of the employee adaptation process to new conditions, which is widely applied in organisational contexts. On the other hand, the article by (Aldemir, 2010), titled *Models and Tools of Change Management: Kotter's 8 Steps Change Model*, outlines *John Kotter's theory of change*, based on eight steps that help effectively implement organisational changes. These stages are:

1. **Create a sense of urgency:** Explain why change is necessary to motivate people to take action.
2. **Build a guiding coalition:** Assemble a group of leaders to drive the change process.
3. **Develop a vision and strategy:** Clearly define the purpose of the change and how to achieve it.

4. **Communicate the vision:** Ensure effective communication so everyone in the organisation understands the purpose and plan of action.
5. **Remove barriers:** Eliminate obstacles and provide support for change efforts.
6. **Generate short-term wins:** Achieve quick successes to build motivation and confidence.
7. **Sustain change:** Maintain momentum and shift the organisational culture to prevent returning to old habits.
8. **Embed change in the culture:** Integrate new practices into the organisation's culture.

Kotter's model pressures emotional and social involvement throughout the change process, making it highly practical in the organisational context.

Based on the analyses conducted in the previous chapters, I believe the following changes should be implemented in the bonus system at *Drug Sales Ltd.*:

1. **External Audit and Performance Evaluation:** The current bonus system relies on self-assessment by sales reps, which can lead to data manipulation. I recommend partnering with an external auditing company to conduct regular customer perspective audits to enhance transparency and ensure more accurate results. An example would be using a mobile app accessible to regular customers. These users would receive a small fee for performing tasks such as taking photos of promotional displays or recording the pharmacist's response to requests for cough medicine recommendations. *Jordan* could leverage this data to generate more reliable reports.
2. **Sales Growth as a Key Metric:** Instead of evaluating sales reps solely on sales volume – which tends to favour reps from more populated regions – I propose rating based on the percentage increase in sales compared to the previous period. This would offer a fairer evaluation of each rep's performance, irrespective of their region.
3. **More Autonomy for Sales Reps:** I suggest introducing periodic meetings where sales reps can share their opinions and suggestions on procedures. Based on this feedback, management could update processes to make them more efficient. Additionally, this collaborative approach would increase reps' sense of responsibility and personal contribution to the company's success, thereby improving their trust in management.

- 4. Leaderboard and Cooperation:** Implementing a leaderboard for sales reps, where the top performers can assist those at the bottom, would foster healthy competition while promoting cooperation. This system would also recognise top employees and offer them development opportunities through training. As a result, management would gain better insight into which employees are suitable for promotion, boosting motivation and loyalty within the organisation.

Introducing organisational changes, particularly in areas like bonus systems, is a complex process that requires a well-developed plan and a thoughtful approach to people. The *Lewin* and *Kotter models* offer a solid theoretical foundation for managing this process. However, in practice, they must be tailored to the organisation's specific context and employees' individual needs. A key aspect of this process is persuading people to embrace change, often involving stepping out of their comfort zones and adapting to new circumstances. As managers, we must recognise that each individual responds to change differently, and the adaptation process requires patience and a personalised approach.

Change is neither easy nor immediate, so it is crucial to allow adequate implementation time and monitor its effects before comparing results. In the context of the bonus system at *Drug Sales Ltd.*, the proposed changes – such as external audits, assessments based on sales growth, and giving sales reps more autonomy – can significantly enhance employee motivation and engagement. Implementing these changes in a personalised manner, considering the different reactions of employees, will help minimise resistance and increase the effectiveness of the process.

Moreover, it is important to remember that change management involves the technical implementation of new solutions and providing psychological support to employees throughout the process. Numerous studies highlight effective methods for convincing people to change and minimising resistance, and these practical strategies can be crucial in any organisational transformation. Ultimately, the success of change implementation depends on the ability to understand the needs and expectations of employees. This makes change management not only an operational challenge but also a process that requires skill in working with people.

Part B: Psychological Contract

A psychological contract is “not a written document but implies a series of mutual expectations and satisfaction of needs arising from the people–organisation relationship” (Mullins, 2010, p.14). It is not a formal, written agreement but includes a series of expectations regarding rights, privileges, duties, and obligations that, while informal, significantly influence people’s behaviour.

In our case, the scenario highlights issues with an inappropriate bonus structure that employees perceive as unfair. Previously, the system favoured those working in more populated areas, but now it functions as a complete roulette. Moreover, the company has introduced new skill requirements without providing evidence of adequate training or guidance to help employees meet these expectations.

The current motivation system drives employees to focus on piecework, prioritising completing as many calls as possible, often sacrificing quality. Employees carry out their duties mechanically, concentrating primarily on following procedures – or just giving the impression of doing so – resulting in a lack of genuine commitment.

Employees operate as individual sales representatives, working independently to achieve their goals, which are not always aligned with the organisation's objectives. This gap stems from a poorly designed bonus system that fails to incentivise actions supporting the company's strategy.

My conclusions above are just assumptions based on the provided Scenario. They highlight an apparent conflict between employee goals based on the bonus structure and company goals.

My proposed changes to the bonus system, provided in the previous chapter, should theoretically restore balance to the company's psychological contract with employees.

In summary, the psychological contract in the analysed organisation requires immediate attention due to the evident conflict between employee expectations and company goals.

The proposed changes, including external audits, sales growth as a key metric, increased autonomy for sales representatives, and a leaderboard system, aim to rebuild trust and restore balance in the employee-organisation relationship.

These initiatives can improve transparency, motivation, and employee engagement while aligning with the company's long-term goals. Moreover, their implementation could boost efficiency and rebuild employee trust in management and the company.

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